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From Customer Projects to ECTS

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ABSTRACT

Lapland UAS has a long tradition in Project-Based Learning (PBL). In the ICT department, PBL is implemented into the semester projects. Course integration offers an opportunity to develop the skills of both students and teachers by using new technologies and developing innovations. The integration of study courses provides additional resources for EU funded R&D projects of ICT department.

The R&D project named RURAL-IoT started in Autumn 2018. The R&D personnel contacted the department suggesting a collaboration. The 6th-semester project was selected to develop new ideas. The RURAL-IoT project's target was to create new innovations using low cost, low power and mobile IoT technologies usable in Lapland's rural areas. The lack of an electricity distribution infrastructure and poor mobile telecommunication connections are challenging. Student projects were run by the Agile SCRUM way.

During the project, two questionnaires were prepared to 3rd year students. The first was a self-assessment survey to study the level of students' innovation competence at the beginning of the project. The second survey was conducted to find how innovation competencies were developed during the project. The R&D and teaching team were interviewed to find out their ideas about integrated learning project as well as how useful they thought this kind of integrated learning case was.

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This document describes the background of integrated learning and R&D-project. The results of students' innovation competence development, as well as experiences of the project staff and teachers, are also described.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Innovative technologies

Internet of Things is one of the megatrends that make digitalization possible. Megatrends like robotics, IoT, artificial intelligence, and big data go hand in hand. These megatrends act as drivers for the development of sensor and network technologies and data analytics. With the advancement, the sensors become cheaper and their size decreases while data transmission speeds up and data can be processed in large quantities in real time without investing in heavy IT infrastructure. Even small software vendors can make globally scalable solutions with existing technologies.

Arctic, harsh, and rural conditions require a long battery life from the IoT device. Data must be capable of being transmitted over long distances. Devices should also withstand low temperatures during the winter and direct sunshine in the summer time.

1.2. Semester project – Case Rural IoT

The Spring 2019 Learning project task for the 6th semester was a part of “RURAL IoT (IoT innovations for Sensing and Positioning in Rural Areas)” -R&D project funded by Regional Council of Lapland. The main idea of the “RURAL IoT-project” was to develop new innovations to Lapland that can utilize cheap, low power consumption and mobile IoT-technologies. The RURAL-IoT project aimed to integrate the interests of both the R&D-project and the teaching.

During the project, two pilot projects were finished. In the first pilot project, new technologies were tested in the oldest and still vital source of livelihoods in the North, reindeer herding. One of the biggest challenges in reindeer herding is that there have always been carnivores in the reindeer husbandry area. Wolverines, bears, wolves and golden eagles have taken their share of the reindeer [1] In the pilot project a real-time solution to follow the location and the body temperature of the reindeer was developed.

For the second pilot project students developed new ideas to utilize IoT-solutions and finally designed and made a prototype. Student teams had to take into account cold climate, power consumption, and radio network coverage in the Northern periphery. In the given task students were to brainstorm a device that can monitor surroundings, is low-power and cheap and uses Low-Power Wide-Area Networks (*LPWA networks*) [2]. Other requirements for the prototype were to develop a mobile application including a real-time clock, GPS, temperature and humidification, ie. sensors, the basic architecture is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The Architecture of RURAL IoT

1.3. Integrated courses

The ICT Curriculum is based on semester projects due to results of piloting other options as well [3]. The learning project is supported by semester courses that are integrated into the project to meet learning outcomes.

Project-based learning (PBL) is used to integrate theoretical and practical content in a real-world context. It increases students' motivation and participation [4, 5]. The integrated learning project called "RURAL IoT" as shown in Fig. 2 consisted of five PBL courses, each 5 ECTS:

1. Professional Project Management
2. Communication skills
3. Advanced Mobile Technologies
4. System Laboratories
5. Management and Leadership

Fig. 2. The Integrated learning project.

At the end of the semester, students arranged a public exhibition called “SMART ICT EXHIBITION 2019” to show prototypes they developed.

1.4. Research questions

The study aimed to seek answers to questions about whether students can sufficiently innovate, even if the technology has already been defined in advance. Has there been any change in results between the start and end questionnaire of the project? The research will also address their experience in teamwork and problem-solving skills. Instructors were asked about students’ attitude and initiative.

2. MEASURING INNOVATION SKILLS

2.1. Data collection

In this research, the target group was the same as in the previous study about the innovation skills [7]. To be comparable the survey was based on the same questions developed in the ESF (*European Social Fund*) project [8] as it was in the previous study. The questions measure the development of students’ innovation competencies as self-assessment. There were 22 questions about the following topics: Ability to creative problem-solving, comprehensiveness, goal orientation, cooperation skills, and networking skills.

The same five questions related to teamwork and innovation were chosen again for students:

- Q1: I present ideas on how the task could be carried out for the approval of others
- Q2: I present new, practical solutions for meeting the goal

- Q3: I show interest in the subject
- Q4: I act persistently for meeting the goal(s)
- Q5: I take my group members ideas into account

In addition to previous questions to students, questions Q3 and Q4 were also asked from instructors to find out their opinion about student’s attitude and initiative. Questions were sent by email to eight teachers and/or instructors. Replies returned (N=6) by the deadline were taken into account in this study

2.2. Results

Results of the year 2018 (4th semester) survey are used as a baseline and reference results. The initial survey of the 6th semester was carried out at the start of the RURAL-IoT project in January 2019 and the final survey was done at the end of the project in April 2019. All surveys were conducted to the same student group. Total 18 students completed the start questionnaire and 19 students answered to the final questionnaire. The survey was carried out using the Webropol online survey tool.

Table 1. Results of the questionnaire. The data are presented as frequencies and percentages of the total amount.

	Not at all	Poor	Moderate	Good	Excellent
Q1: I present ideas on how the task could be carried out for the approval of others					
<i>Baseline (N=24)</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	14 (58%)	6 (25%)
<i>Beginning of the project (N=18)</i>	0	0	5 (28%)	11 (61%)	2 (11%)
<i>After the project completion (N=19)</i>	0	0	3 (16%)	11 (58%)	5 (26%)
Q2: I present new, practical solutions for meeting the goal					
<i>Baseline (N=24)</i>	0	1 (4%)	2 (8%)	12 (50%)	9 (38%)
<i>Beginning of the project (N=18)</i>	1 (5%)	0	4 (22%)	10 (56%)	3 (17%)
<i>After the project completion (N=19)</i>	0	0	6 (31%)	3 (16%)	10 (53%)
Q3: I show interest in the subject					
<i>Baseline (N=24)</i>	0	0	6 (25%)	13 (54%)	5 (21%)
<i>Beginning of the project (N=18)</i>	0	1 (5%)	7 (39%)	7 (39%)	3 (17%)
<i>After the project completion (N=19)</i>	1 (5%)	0	6 (43%)	5 (26%)	7 (37%)
Q4: I act persistently for meeting the goal(s)					
<i>Baseline (N=24)</i>	0	0	4 (17%)	10 (42%)	10 (42%)
<i>Beginning of the project</i>	0	2 (11%)	3 (17%)	8 (44%)	5 (28%)
<i>After the project completion (N=19)</i>	0	0	3 (16%)	8 (42%)	8 (42%)
Q5: I take my group members ideas into account					

Baseline (N=24)	0	0	4 (17%)	9 (38%)	11 (46%)
Beginning of the project (N=18)	1 (6%)	0	2 (11%)	7 (39%)	8 (44%)
After the project completion (N=19)	0	0	2 (10%)	7 (37%)	10 (53%)

Two of the questions in figure 3 were taken into a closer look. Students' own opinions about both initiative skills and perseverance in problem-solving skills decreased at the beginning of the project compared to the baseline in the previous year. However, they were recovered at the end of the project.

Fig 3. Development of students' initiative skills and perseverance in problem-solving.

3. SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The conclusions of the surveys are contradictory. It seems that the confidence of students to their own substance knowledge would have deteriorated compared to the previous questionnaire. According to the survey results, one might assume that the rise in the level of requirements of the project would be a reason for the students to feel uncertain about their skills. According to questionnaires to instructors, students did not “want” to use instructors' expertise in problem-solving at the beginning. This problem was identified at an early stage when project teams were offered lessons and tutorials related to the assignment. After that, the instructors felt that the threshold to ask for guidance decreased significantly. Social interaction was likely to become easier when the instructors became more familiar.

The development of students' skills and motivation was also evaluated on the basis of the final survey, which was conducted among teachers and instructors of the project. The queries concerned student questions Q3 and Q4.

Based on the results, it seems that the assessment of the students' motivation by the instructors was positive (Q3). However, in their opinion, motivation was more visible at the group level. Personal motivation within groups varied greatly.

Question Q4 focused on students' perseverance to pursue goals. All the respondents felt that groups were persistent and aiming for goals. One of the respondents notes that some technical options were abandoned if the schedule for its implementation was not realistic to them

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